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Generating Stable and Metastable Critical Points in Uncertain Systems via Flow-based Models

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Abstract

This work proposes the use of conditional flow-based generative models to learn an approximation of the distribution of the critical points of a cost function. This approximation is used to incrementally identify all critical points, in the feasible domain of said function, by iteratively alternating the sampling of the distribution and the retraining of the model with the newly discovered points. This paper will focus, in particular, on the identification and conditional generation of all local minima in the case in which the value of the cost function is subject to some uncertain parameters. The target application is the study of complex dynamical systems. It will be shown that when the cost function represents the potential of a dynamical system, the proposed flow-based model can be used to generate minima conditional to their degree of stability or metastability.

In dynamical systems subject to uncertainty in the dynamics, the existence of the minima and their stability characteristics are a function of the uncertain parameters. Thus, the proposed model architecture incorporates a conditional variable that can be the value of the uncertain parameters or a label indicating a characteristic of the critical points. The proposed conditional flow-model allows the generation of points with the desired characteristics. This is of extreme importance in the analysis of equilibrium states and possible transitions, controlled or uncontrolled, to other equilibrium states.

Some illustrative examples of functions with hundreds of local minima are used to test the potentialities of the proposed approach. It will be shown that the use of a generative approach is advantageous to explore more complex landscapes compared to a basic random local search algorithm. When applied to the analysis of the uncertain five body problem, the proposed generative model is shown to successfully identify all dynamical equilibrium solutions under uncertainty. Finally when trained on the dynamical stability properties of the critical points, the model can successfully differentiate between stable and metastable solutions. These results show that, for certain types of system, the flow-based model can be trained to find equilibrium points more efficiently than a simple random search. Moreover, we demonstrate that conditional flow-based models are capable of one-shot sampling for specific values of uncertain parameters or characteristics of the equilibrium points.

KEYWORDS

dynamical systems, flow-based models, conditional generation, metastability

1 | INTRODUCTION

Machine Learning (ML) methods are now commonplace in many areas of science to analyse systems that are difficult to study with conventional approaches. Such methods are useful for extracting patterns in data, which has very wide ranging applications. One area that shows potential

to benefit from ML is the study of dynamical systems. These mathematical models can describe the behaviour of many real-world systems ranging in scale from molecular to cosmological systems. Many real examples of such systems are difficult to study analytically and so data-driven methods such as ML are used. In addition, theories from the study of dynamical systems have influenced certain ML architectures. For example, Neural ODEs substitute the discrete time transformations of architectures such as residual networks with a continuous-time parameterisation as an Ordinary Differential Equation (ODE) (Chen, Rubanova,

Bettencourt, & Duvenaud, 2018). As well as their use in supervised learning problems, these models can learn a latent function for continuous time-series generation (Rubanova, Chen, & Duvenaud, 2019). Another popular ML architecture that takes inspiration from dynamical systems is the Physics Informed Neural Network (PINN) (Cuomo et al., 2022). Similarly to Neural ODEs, PINNs can be used to approximate transient dynamics of a system by incorporating known physics of the system into learning. Both of these architectures provide a means of efficiently propagating highly complex dynamical systems with applications including modelling fluid flows (Rojas, Dengel, & Ribeiro, 2021; Linot & Graham, 2023), molecular dynamics (Islam, Thakur, Mojmuder, & Hasan, 2021; Seifner & Sanchez, 2023), and turbulent plasma dynamics (Mathews et al., 2021).

An area of machine learning that has progressively gained interest in the fields of chemistry and biology is generative AI. Generative AI is widely used to generate new images and videos and sits at the foundation of all large language models. Common generative architectures are Generative Adversarial Network (GAN) (Goodfellow et al., 2014), and Variational Auto-Encoder (VAE) (Kingma & Welling, 2022). More recently, Denoising Diffusion Probabilistic Models (DDPMs) have shown state-of-the-art performance in generating photorealistic images (Ho, Jain, & Abbeel, 2020). A DDPM is trained by progressively adding noise to training data and learning the inverse transformation from pure noise to the original training data. Although these are capable of generating high-quality samples, the process of generation in these models can be computationally expensive (Shih, Belkhale, Ermon, Sadigh, & Anari, 2023).

Another interesting class of generative models are flow-based models. Flow-based models, also referred to as normalising flows, are a type of generative model whose main feature is that they directly approximate the density of the posterior distribution (Rezende & Mohamed, 2015). The transformation from prior distribution to posterior distribution is invertible and so does not require a separate encoder and decoder architecture. With appropriate design of the invertible transformation, the Jacobian of the transformation can be easy to calculate to give exact likelihood estimation (Dinh, Krueger, & Bengio, 2015). These types of generative models have also seen improvements that allow them to scale well to large problems, such as with Real-NVP (Dinh, Sohl-Dickstein, & Bengio, 2017) and GLOW (Kingma & Dhariwal, 2018). One of the advantages of the exact likelihood estimation of flow-based models is that they can be used for variational inference with an arbitrarily complex posterior distribution (Rezende & Mohamed, 2015). This allows the model to learn not only from samples from the target distribution, but also directly from the unnormalised density of the distribution where this is available.

In most applications of generative models we are interested in generating outputs that are conditioned on some input. For example, when generating an image it may be conditioned on a text description. In other cases, the conditional variable might be categorical such that samples are generated with a certain class label. The work of (van Engelen & Hoos, 2020) provides a unified view on classification and generation in

the context of semi-supervised learning. When a generative model is predicated on a label, it can be used both to generate conditional samples and for classification. One of the simplest examples of conditional generation is in the conditional GAN (Mirza & Osindero, 2014). This uses a concatenation of the label and noise as input to the generator such that its output is conditioned on the label. In the approach of CatGAN in (Springenberg, 2016), the discriminator loss includes a cross-entropy term for classifying true data points.

Other works have used flow-based models for conditional generation and classification. The work of (Atanov, Volokhova, Ashukha, Sosnovik, & Vetrov, 2020) introduced a formulation of self-supervised learning using flow-based models. This architecture defines a joint likelihood for features and labels. It is referred to as “semi-conditional” since the condition on labels is only incorporated into some of the model’s layers. Another similar approach combined flow-based models with generalised linear models to learn conditional distributions (Nalisnick, Matsukawa, Teh, Gorur, & Lakshminarayanan, 2019). Similarly to the semi-conditional flow, this model adds a classifier on a deep feature representation of the data. An alternative approach that allows direct sampling of specific classes is presented in (Izmailov, Kirichenko, Finzi, & Wilson, 2020). This uses a Gaussian Mixture Model (GMM) as the prior distribution with the number of mixture components equal to the number of classes. The loss includes a “consistency regularisation” term that motivates the model to give the same label for perturbed, unlabelled data such that it can learn in a semi-supervised manner.

This work investigates the potential for using generative models to find all critical points, with given properties, of a multimodal function $g(\mathbf{x})$. The key assumption is that critical points are distributed according to an underlying structure dictated by the function $g(\mathbf{x})$. The target application is the study of complex dynamical systems where $g(\mathbf{x})$ is a potential function and critical points are stable, unstable or metastable states, or $g(\mathbf{x})$ is a functional whose critical points represent periodic orbits. Unlike other works that aimed at learning a surrogate model of $g(\mathbf{x})$, the goal of this work is to directly learn an approximation of the distribution of the critical points of $g(\mathbf{x})$ starting from an already observed subset of them. The idea is reminiscent of the concept of Estimation of Distribution in Evolutionary Computing, though the objective of this work is to discover sets of critical points with given properties rather than finding the global minimum of $g(\mathbf{x})$ or the Pareto optimal set of a multi-objective problem. We also assume that in general evaluating the function $g(\mathbf{x})$ multiple times is more expensive than training a generative model and, therefore, it is desirable to directly sample where, in the space of \mathbf{x} , the critical points are likely to be. Furthermore, assessing the properties of the critical points might require expensive calculations, hence it is desirable to directly generate the points conditional to the properties of interest.

This problem is formulated as modelling a probability distribution that has a high density at the location of critical points. To approximate the distribution, we propose the use of flow-based models (Papamakarios, Nalisnick, Rezende, Mohamed, & Lakshminarayanan, 2021). The approach to conditional generation used in this work is

similar to that of conditional GLOW (Zhu, Zabaras, Koutsourelakis, & Perdikaris, 2019). In this case the model includes an encoding of the conditional input that extracts multiscale features of the input. The flow-based model then aims to predict the output of the system conditioned on these features. Since the goal of the work presented here is to generate samples conditioned on certain parameters, flow-based models provide a suitably flexible architecture for conditional generation that does not require an explicit classification loss.

As an illustrative example, we apply this idea to the discovery of all the minima of three benchmark functions, with hundreds of critical points, and three different underlying structures. We will show that, depending on the structure of $g(x)$, the use of a flow model is more efficient than a systematic search by uniformly sampling the parameter space. We will also show that the use of a flow model can be significantly more efficient when the structure of the function $g(x)$ is affected by uncertainty or changes according to one or more parameters. We also apply the method to the astrodynamics problem of finding equilibrium points in the Circular Restricted Five-Body Problem (CR5BP) (Zotos & Suraj, 2018). This is a restricted case of the N-body problem that considers the motion of an object with respect to four primary bodies in a planar configuration. In this case the existence of minima and their stability properties are dependent on the relative mass of the gravitational bodies, which can be known only with a degree of uncertainty. The final test case is a highly simplified dynamical system with a metastable equilibrium point, which is a critical point that can exhibit both stable and unstable behaviour. The stability is affected by a parameter that changes the shape of the potential function. We will show how one can sample the equilibrium points conditional to the desired stability in the case of an uncertain parameter.

The remainder of this paper is organised as follows. Section 2 presents related work in this area. Section 3 describes the generative model architecture and the proposed approach to training this model. Section 4 presents the problem definition for the each of the test cases followed by results. Section 5 gives conclusions and recommendations for future work.

2 | RELATED WORK

The use of generative models to study dynamical systems is still in its infancy. Recent examples of the use of unsupervised learning to generate trajectories in the Restricted Circular Three Body Problem can be found in (Bonasera, 2022), while an example of the use of generative models in conjunction analysis can be found in (Stevenson, Rodriguez-Fernandez, Urrutxua, & Camacho, 2023). Within the framework of the Circular Restricted Three-Body Problem, Support Vector Machines have been utilised to classify transit orbits (A. Li, 2015) and generative architectures based on Conditional Variational Autoencoders (CVAEs) have been developed for the generation of periodic solutions and diffusion

models have been recently employed to explore the space of global optimal solutions of low-thrust indirect trajectory optimisation problems (Beeson, Li, & Sinha, 2024; Graebner & Beeson, 2025).

Other applications of ML methods to dynamical systems have focussed on creating reduced order models, both through deep learning and simpler ML systems (Ghadami & Epureanu, 2022). These models are useful for propagating complex systems or deriving controllers for such systems. For example, in (Watter, Springenberg, Boedecker, & Riedmiller, 2015) the authors create a latent embedding of image trajectories using variational autoencoders such that these trajectories are locally linear. This allows the use of conventional optimal control methods for solving complex non-linear problems. The methods proposed here focus more specifically on finding solutions to dynamical systems without directly modelling the transient behaviour of the system.

The problem of finding equilibrium points can be formulated as a global search problem. Specifically, we are interested in finding all minima within a domain. This presents a different set of challenges to algorithms that aim to converge to a single global optimum. There are certain classes of population-based methods of global optimisation that aim to find multiple solutions within multimodal problems, such as species-based evolutionary algorithms (J.-P. Li, Li, & Wood, 2010). These maintain separate populations, or “species” of solutions between generations thus ensuring a diversity of generated solutions. Another class of evolutionary methods that is conceptually similar to the approach proposed in this work is Estimation of Distribution Algorithms (EDAs) (Hauschild & Pelikan, 2011). These methods maintain a probabilistic model of potential solutions that can be sampled to generate new solutions. This results in an iterative approach of updating and sampling the distribution. The parameterisation of this distribution can take some different forms, such as a bayesian network (Kaedi & Ahn, 2017), but the distribution should be easy to update and sample. This is conceptually similar to the flow-based model, which is designed to be easily updated via maximum-likelihood training and samples from a simple prior distribution. However, the model proposed here allows for conditional generation that is otherwise difficult with most global search methods.

Various machine learning methods including flow-based models have been used to approximate energy surfaces in large scale problems, which can then in turn be used for finding equilibrium solutions. This was used in atomistic simulations of molecules, where the complex interactions between many particles in a structure are difficult to model analytically (Behler, 2015). Earlier research in this area used generic ML function approximators including artificial neural networks to model potential surfaces (Behler & Parrinello, 2007). It is also possible to incorporate physics information into the training of these representations via PINNs (Pun, Batra, Ramprasad, & Mishin, 2019). Although these methods are effective at approximating potential functions, they do not allow for direct sampling of these distributions. This is where generative ML methods are used. One such example used flow-based models to generate stable molecular structures (Noé, Olsson, Köhler, & Wu, 2019). In

this case the model samples from a Boltzmann distribution that minimizes the free-energy of a system. This demonstrated the applicability of flow-based models to generating new solutions in high-dimensional systems that are otherwise expensive to model. Other work used a diffusion based approach, combined with function approximators tailored to molecular structures, to sample complex equilibrium distributions (Zheng et al., 2024). Although the diffusion model does allow for density estimation, this requires the solution of an ODE that tracks the distribution change compared to the simpler density estimation of flow-based models. In addition, the diffusion model allows for “property-guided” generation that conditions the output on some desired properties. This conditional generation requires a classifier model to score the output given a conditional label. As discussed above, other approaches to conditional generation, including the approach described in this work, do not require a separate classifier.

The work in this paper expands on previous work by the authors where only the classification and generation of stable and unstable points in the n-body problem was attempted (Wilson & Vasile, 2024).

3 | METHODS

3.1 | Flow-based Generative Model

Flow-based generative models transform a prior distribution $p_{\mathbf{Z}}(\mathbf{z})$ through a series of invertible transformations to a target distribution $p_{\mathbf{X}}(\mathbf{x})$ (Kobyzev, Prince, & Brubaker, 2021). The random variable $\mathbf{Z} \in \mathbb{R}^D$ has a known and tractable distribution and the transformation is defined as $\mathbf{Z} = f(\mathbf{X})$. The change of variable rule gives the following expression for the probability density of \mathbf{X} :

$$p_{\mathbf{X}}(\mathbf{x}) = p_{\mathbf{Z}}(f(\mathbf{x})) |\det Df(\mathbf{x})| \quad (1)$$

where $Df(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{\partial f(\mathbf{x})}{\partial \mathbf{x}}$ is the Jacobian of f at \mathbf{x} . To generate a sample \mathbf{x} from \mathbf{X} , one can first sample from the simpler distribution of \mathbf{Z} and then transform this sample via $\mathbf{x} = f^{-1}(\mathbf{z})$. This is the main benefit of flow-based models, where the transformation f represents a “flow” from a potentially intractable distribution to a much simpler one.

Several different architectures exist for defining flow-based generative models (Papamakarios et al., 2021). The architecture used here is called Non-linear Independent Components Estimation (NICE) (Dinh et al., 2015), which is a volume-preserving flow since the prior distribution has the same dimensionality as the target, $f : \mathbb{R}^D \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^D$. The transformation f is a composition of several “layers” of transformations $f = f_L \circ \dots \circ f_2 \circ f_1$. Each transformation is a bijective coupling layer with a tractable inverse and unit Jacobian determinant.

The output of layer f_i is denoted $h^{(i)}$, where $h^{(0)} = \mathbf{x}$. To make each layer invertible, the input is divided into two parts: h_{l_1} and h_{l_2} where the indexes l_1 and l_2 define how the vector is split. For the two-dimensional problems considered here, where $\mathbf{x} = (x, y)$, this is simply the first and second terms, i.e. $h_{l_1}^{(0)} = x$ and $h_{l_2}^{(0)} = y$. The additive coupling law is

defined as

$$h_{l_1}^{(i+1)} = h_{l_2}^{(i)}, \quad (2)$$

$$h_{l_2}^{(i+1)} = h_{l_1}^{(i)} + m^{(i)}(h_{l_2}^{(i)}), \quad (3)$$

where m is a non-linear function defined for each coupling layer. This function is parameterised as a Deep Neural Network (DNN) such that each m is trainable.

Since each coupling layer is designed to have unit Jacobian determinant, these layers alone do not allow for scaling of the inputs. Therefore, an additional scaling layer is used in the output of the NICE model. This scaling layer has the form

$$\mathbf{z} = S \odot h^{(L)}, \quad (4)$$

where S is a diagonal scaling matrix with $S_{ii} = e^{s_i}$, $i = 1, \dots, D$. One other distinguishing feature of NICE is it uses a prior distribution that is factorial, i.e.

$$p_{\mathbf{Z}}(\mathbf{z}) = \prod_{i=1}^D p_{z_i}(z_i). \quad (5)$$

Here a logistic distribution is used as the prior:

$$p_{z_i}(z_i) = \frac{e^{-z_i/\sigma_i}}{\sigma_i (1 + e^{-z_i/\sigma_i})^2}, \quad (6)$$

where the scaling parameters, denoted σ_i are also trainable parameters of the model. Since this distribution is factorial, this results in the “NICE criterion” shown in (7) that defines the log-likelihood of the modelled distribution.

$$\log(p_{\mathbf{X}}(\mathbf{x})) = \sum_{i=1}^D [\log(p_{z_i}(f(\mathbf{x})_i)) + \log(|S_{ii}|)] \quad (7)$$

Training aims to maximise the log-likelihood of sampled points $\mathbf{x} \sim p_{\mathbf{X}}$ in the model as defined by the NICE criterion. The objective is then defined as

$$\max_{\theta} \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{x} \sim p_{\mathbf{X}}} \sum_{i=1}^D [\log(p_{z_i}(f(\mathbf{x})_i)) + \log(|S_{ii}|)], \quad (8)$$

where θ denotes the trainable parameters of the model. This maximum likelihood objective only requires samples from the posterior distribution without any knowledge of the structure of the distribution. In the applications considered here, we can define the posterior distribution up to a normalising constant that is a priori unknown. One way of incorporating this information into the flow model training is referred to as the Evidence Error Loss (EEL) (Raveri, Doux, & Pandey, 2024). Let $\tilde{p}_{\mathbf{X}}(\mathbf{x})$ denote the unnormalised posterior density. The EEL objective can be expressed as

$$\max_{\theta} \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{x} \sim p_{\mathbf{X}}} \left[\log \left(\frac{q_{\theta}(\mathbf{x})}{\tilde{p}_{\mathbf{X}}(\mathbf{x})} \right) - \log \hat{\mathcal{Z}}(\mathbf{x}) \right]^2, \quad (9)$$

where $q_{\theta}(\mathbf{x})$ denotes the estimated density of the flow model at \mathbf{x} as defined in equation (7) and

$$\log \hat{\mathcal{Z}}(\mathbf{x}) = \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{x} \sim p_{\mathbf{X}}} \left[\log \left(\frac{q_{\theta}(\mathbf{x})}{\tilde{p}_{\mathbf{X}}(\mathbf{x})} \right) \right]. \quad (10)$$

3.2 | Conditional Flow-based Generative Model

A conditional flow-based model aims to model a probability conditioned on a variable $\mathbf{c} \in \mathbf{C}$. This variable can be some parameter of the target distribution, or a label to define classes of points in the distribution. The target distribution has the form $p_{\mathbf{X}}(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{c})$. In this formulation of conditional model, the conditional variable \mathbf{c} is included in the transformation f . Equation (1) can then be rewritten as

$$p_{\mathbf{X}}(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{c}) = p_{\mathbf{Z}}(f(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{c})) \det |\mathbf{D}f(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{c})|. \quad (11)$$

At each coupling layer, the input to m is concatenated with \mathbf{c} such that Eqs. (2) and (3) become

$$h_{i_1}^{(l+1)} = h_{i_2}^{(l)}, \quad (12)$$

$$h_{i_2}^{(l+1)} = h_{i_1}^{(l)} + m^{(l)} \left(\begin{bmatrix} h_{i_2}^{(l)} & \mathbf{c} \end{bmatrix} \right). \quad (13)$$

This maintains the unit Jacobian determinant of NICE to allow straightforward density estimation. The conditional NICE criterion then becomes

$$\log(p_{\mathbf{X}}(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{c})) = \sum_{i=1}^D [\log(p_{\mathbf{Z}}(f(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{c}))_i) + \log(|S_{ii}|)] \quad (14)$$

The conditional flow-based model can be trained using both labelled data, where \mathbf{c} is defined for a given sample \mathbf{x} , and unlabelled data. Suppose the training dataset consists of both labelled samples, $(\mathbf{x}_n^l, \mathbf{c}_n^l)$, $n = 1, \dots, N_l$ and unlabelled samples (\mathbf{x}_n^u) , $n = 1, \dots, N_u$ where N_l and N_u denote the number of labelled and unlabelled samples respectively. The log-likelihood of labelled samples can be determined directly via equation (14). For unlabelled samples, the variable \mathbf{c} for each sample is assigned the value that gives the maximum likelihood:

$$\mathbf{c}^u = \arg \max_{\mathbf{c} \in \mathbf{C}} \sum_{i=1}^D [\log(p_{\mathbf{Z}}(f(\mathbf{x}^u, \mathbf{c}))_i) + \log(|S_{ii}|)]. \quad (15)$$

When \mathbf{C} is a set of categorical variables, the maximum argument can be found by enumerating over all values of \mathbf{C} . Training aims to maximise the likelihood of both labelled and unlabelled points:

$$\begin{aligned} \max_{\theta} \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{x} \sim p_{\mathbf{X}}, \mathbf{c} \in \mathbf{C}} \sum_{i=1}^D [\log(p_{\mathbf{Z}}(f(\mathbf{x}^l, \mathbf{c}^l))_i) + \log(|S_{ii}|)] \\ + \sum_{i=1}^D [\log(p_{\mathbf{Z}}(f(\mathbf{x}^u, \mathbf{c}^u))_i) + \log(|S_{ii}|)]. \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

3.3 | Training Procedure

The previous sections define the model architecture and objective functions for flow-based and conditional flow-based models. This section describes the different procedures for training these models. The aim of training is to learn a model that samples near the desired equilibrium points, denoted \mathbf{s} , with high probability. The descriptions that follow are for the general case of finding minima of a cost function $g(\mathbf{x})$, which

can also represent the problem of finding critical points in a dynamical system.

The training dataset, denoted \mathcal{D} , consists of samples around some of the minima \mathbf{s}_k , $k = 1, 2, \dots, N_s$, where N_s is the number of minima represented in the training data. Samples are generated according to a distribution of the form

$$\tilde{p}_{\mathbf{X}}(\mathbf{x}) = \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{s}_k, \Sigma), \quad (17)$$

where \mathcal{N} is a multivariate normal distribution with spherical covariance matrix Σ .

Three different training scenarios are shown here for different formulations of the problem. The initial training dataset will be composed differently depending on the scenario. The three scenarios considered are:

1. The training data contains samples near a subset of the minima and the model must find all minima.
2. The physical space has one or more uncertain parameters and the training data has labels indicating the value of these parameters at the minima.
3. The minima fall under a number of different classes and the training data might contain both labelled and unlabelled samples.

In the following we describe each of these scenarios in more detail.

3.3.1 | Subset of Desired Points

In the first case, the initial training dataset contains samples that are only near a subset of all the desired minima. Starting from these initial points, the model aims to find all minima in the relevant domain. The approach used here iteratively trains and samples the model to expand the dataset such that the learned distribution tends towards the true distribution of minima.

As will be shown, when retraining the model in this manner, information on the relevant function values can be useful for the model's training. Each point in the training data can be associated with a desired point \mathbf{s}_k and then the objective function value, $g(\mathbf{s}_k)$ at the desired point is used as a label for that point. In this case, the posterior distribution of the flow model is over $\hat{\mathbf{x}} = [\mathbf{x} \ g(\mathbf{s}_k)]$.

Prior to training, the initial training dataset is generated by finding N_0 minima from local optimisations starting from uniform samples in the physical space. From each of these points \mathbf{s}_k , $k = 1, 2, \dots, N_0$, a number of samples are drawn from $\mathbf{x} \sim \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{s}_k, \Sigma)$ and added to the training dataset along with their corresponding value of $g(\mathbf{s}_k)$. After defining this initial training dataset, training proceeds as follows:

1. Train model on \mathcal{D} for a defined number of epochs,
2. Sample points in physical space from the flow model and reject samples near existing minima in \mathcal{D} ,
3. Run a local optimisation starting at each of the generated samples,

4. Sample around each of the new minima and add new samples to dataset \mathcal{D} ,
5. Repeat steps 1. to 4.

The loss function associated with the maximum likelihood objective shown in equation 8 can be expressed as

$$L_{ML} = -\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^D [\log(p_{z_i}(f(\mathbf{x}_i))) + \log(|S_{ii}|)], \quad (18)$$

where N denotes the number of points in a minibatch of the training data. Similarly, the EEL objective in equation 9 is given as

$$L_{EEL} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \left[\log \left(\frac{q_{\theta}(\mathbf{x}_i)}{\tilde{p}_{\mathbf{x}}(\mathbf{x}_i)} \right) - \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \left[\log \left(\frac{q_{\theta}(\mathbf{x}_i)}{\tilde{p}_{\mathbf{x}}(\mathbf{x}_i)} \right) \right] \right]^2, \quad (19)$$

where, for each of the points in the dataset, $\tilde{p}_{\mathbf{x}}$ is defined according to equation 17. Since the outputs of the flow-based model have infinite support, but the problems analysed here consider a finite range in \mathbb{R}^D , we add another loss that penalises samples outwith this range. Let x_j^l and x_j^u denote the lower and upper bounds, respectively, of dimension j in physical space. The loss function on samples $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}$ from the model is defined as

$$L_{sample} = \frac{1}{N_{sample}} \sum_{i=1}^{N_{sample}} \sum_{j=1}^D \left[\text{relu}(x_j^l - \tilde{x}_j)^2 + \text{relu}(\tilde{x}_j - x_j^u)^2 \right], \quad (20)$$

where N_{sample} is the number of samples from the model, $\tilde{\mathbf{x}} = f^{-1}(\mathbf{z} \sim p_{\mathbf{z}}(\mathbf{z}))$ denotes a point sampled from the model, and relu is the standard rectified linear function:

$$\text{relu}(x) = \begin{cases} x & x > 0, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (21)$$

After each iteration of training the model for a number of epochs, new points $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}$ are sampled from the model to be used as initial guesses for a local optimisation. Any samples with values outside of the bounds on \mathbf{x} defined by x_j^l and x_j^u are rejected. Additionally, any samples within a threshold distance, denoted r_t , of a known desired point \mathbf{s}_k are rejected, which can be expressed as

$$\|\tilde{\mathbf{x}} - \mathbf{s}_k\| > r_t, \quad k = 1, 2, \dots, N_i \quad (22)$$

where N_i is the total number of found desired points. After running the local optimisation, samples around any new desired points are added to the dataset.

3.3.2 | Uncertain Parameters

When considering a physical system, there are likely to be parameters defining the system's behaviour that are uncertain. In this case, a conditional flow-based model can be trained to learn the conditional distribution of desired points depending on one or more uncertain parameter. The conditional variable \mathbf{c} is then the value of the uncertain parameter(s).

The initial training dataset in this case has samples near desired points for different values of \mathbf{c} . It is assumed here that all desired points are known for the values of \mathbf{c} in the initial training dataset, which can be found via the process described above or otherwise. The model is trained on the entire dataset for a number of epochs with the ML loss based on equation 16 defined as

$$L_{ML} = -\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^D [\log(p_{z_i}(f(\mathbf{x}_i, \mathbf{c}_i))) + \log(|S_{ii}|)], \quad (23)$$

where N is the minibatch size. When generating samples in physical space, the value of \mathbf{c} can be specified or sampled from \mathbf{C} . The sampling loss is calculated as in equation 20 where samples are generated by randomly sampling over \mathbf{C} . Once trained, the model can generate new samples near desired points for values of \mathbf{c} that were not in its training dataset.

3.3.3 | Classes of Points

Each of the desired points can be classified based on characteristics of the points. For example, in dynamical systems, equilibrium points can be classified based on their stability characteristic. In some situations it can be desirable to only generate points of a specific class and so in this case the conditional flow-based model learns the conditional distribution of desired points depending on their class. The conditional variable \mathbf{c} is then categorical and indicates the class to which a point belongs.

The physical parameters described above will also affect the distribution of certain classes of points. To account for the physical parameters, these are included in the posterior distribution of the flow model. Let λ denote the uncertain parameter(s) of the system. The posterior distribution is then over $\hat{\mathbf{x}} = [\mathbf{x} \ \lambda]$.

In this scenario the training data comprises labelled and unlabelled points. For the values of uncertain parameter(s) λ in the training dataset, we again assume that all desired points are known and the dataset consists of samples near these points. For some values of λ all points are labelled and for the other values of λ in the training dataset the corresponding points are unlabelled. Training then proceeds in a semi-supervised manner using both labelled and unlabelled points. The loss corresponding to the objective of equation 16 is the same as in equation 23, where the label \mathbf{c} is either known from the training data for labelled points, or calculated according to equation 15 for unlabelled points. As previously, the sample loss is calculated via equation 20 by randomly sampling over \mathbf{C} .

4 | NUMERICAL EXPERIMENTS

This section presents all numerical experiments used to test the method presented above. We will first present the test functions and the definition of the parameters that affect their structure and the properties of the minima. Note that the function selected for the numerical experiments are intentionally inexpensive, in two dimensions and with

a scalable number of minima. This allows us to easily check that the generative model can exhaustively find all the minima even when the existence of the minima is subject to uncertainty. We will then introduce a metastability problem as an example of cases in which the computation of the desirable properties of a critical point can be expensive. We will then explain the training procedure and present the results of our experiments.

4.1 | Test Cases

Different test cases of varying complexity were used to show the applicability of the methods described above. The Rastrigin, Schwefel, and Whitley functions are benchmark problems that have many local minima. The number of minima can be scaled up or down and their structure can be modified via simple rotation matrix. This makes them suitable as test problems since the search for all the minima can be quite expensive even in two dimensions. The search for minima becomes even more challenging when the number and the rotation of the function are uncertain. Another test case is the Circular Restricted Five-Body Problem (CR5BP), which is a restricted case of the N-body problem in a circular, planar configuration (Ollongren, 1988). The final test case is an example of a potential function that is designed to have a metastable equilibrium point.

4.1.1 | Rastrigin Function

The general D -dimensional form of the Rastrigin function is

$$g(\mathbf{x}) = 10D + \sum_{i=1}^D [x_i^2 - 10 \cos(2\pi x_i)]. \quad (24)$$

In this work we include a parameter, ω that affects how the minima are distributed. Equation 24 then becomes

$$g(\mathbf{x}) = 10D + \sum_{i=1}^D [x_i^2 - 10 \cos(2\pi\omega x_i)]. \quad (25)$$

We also use the function's partial derivatives when running local minimisations as these can also be used when studying dynamical systems.

The Jacobian of equation 25 is

$$\mathbf{J}_i(\mathbf{x}) = 2x_i + 20\pi\omega \sin(2\pi\omega x_i), \quad (26)$$

and its Hessian is

$$\mathbf{H}_{ii}(\mathbf{x}) = 2 + 40\pi^2\omega^2 \cos(2\pi\omega x_i), \quad (27)$$

where the Hessian is diagonal due to the separability of the problem.

We seek all points $\mathbf{x} \in \mathcal{X}$, where $\mathcal{X} \subset \mathbb{R}^D$, such that $g(\mathbf{x})$ is a local minimum. In the two-dimensional case, we define $x_1 = x$ and $x_2 = y$. This function has a global minimum of $g(\mathbf{x}) = 0$ at $(x, y) = (0, 0)$. Figure 1 shows the values of $g(\mathbf{x})$ and locations of local minima over the domain $x, y \in [-1, 1]$ for a value of $\omega = 3.5$.

FIGURE 1 Value of the Rastrigin function $g(x, y)$ and locations of local minima for $\omega = 3.5$.

4.1.2 | Schwefel Function

To avoid numerical issues with the Hessian at values of $x_i = 0$, we use a simplified form of the function considering only values of $x_i \geq \delta x > 0$. In this case the general D -dimensional form of the Schwefel function is

$$g(\mathbf{x}) = 418.9829D - \sum_{i=1}^D [x_i \sin(\sqrt{x_i})]. \quad (28)$$

Including the parameter ω in the same manner as in the Rastrigin function gives the following:

$$g(\mathbf{x}) = 418.9829D - \sum_{i=1}^D [\omega x_i \sin(\sqrt{\omega x_i})]. \quad (29)$$

The Jacobian and Hessian for this function are shown in (30) and (31). As with the Rastrigin function, the problem is separable and so has a diagonal Hessian.

$$\mathbf{J}_i(\mathbf{x}) = -\frac{\omega^3 x_i^2 \sqrt{\omega x_i} \cos(\sqrt{\omega x_i})}{2(\omega x_i)^{3/2}} - \omega \sin(\sqrt{\omega x_i}) \quad (30)$$

$$\mathbf{H}_{ii}(\mathbf{x}) = \omega^{3/2} \frac{(\sqrt{\omega x_i} \sin(\sqrt{\omega x_i}) - 3 \cos(\sqrt{\omega x_i}))}{4\sqrt{x_i}} \quad (31)$$

We seek all points $\mathbf{x} \in \mathcal{X}$, where $\mathcal{X} \subset \mathbb{R}^D$, such that $g(\mathbf{x})$ is a local minimum. To use the same domain as the Rastrigin function of $x, y \in [-1, 1]$, values of x_i are shifted in the negative direction by $1 + \delta x$. Figure 2 shows the values of $g(\mathbf{x})$ and local minima for the Schwefel function over this domain where $\omega = 1100$ and $\delta x = 10/\omega$.

4.1.3 | Whitley Function

This test function is a composition of two other benchmark functions: Griewank's function and one of De Jong's test suite of functions. It was

FIGURE 2 Value of the Schwefel function $g(x, y)$ and locations of local minima for $\omega = 1100$.

originally introduced in (Whitley, Rana, Dzubera, & Mathias, 1996) as a suitable test problem for Evolutionary Algorithms (EAs) that is non-separable and has many local minima.

Using the same notation as in the original work, De Jong's function $F2$ in two dimensions is defined as

$$F2(x_1, x_2) = 100(x_1^2 - x_2)^2 + (1 - x_1)^2 \quad (32)$$

and Griewank's function $F8$ in one dimension is defined as

$$F8(x) = 1 + \frac{x^2}{4000} - \cos(x). \quad (33)$$

Then the general D -dimensional composition of these functions can be expressed as

$$F(\mathbf{x}) = F8(F2(x_n, x_1)) + \sum_{i=1}^{D-1} F8(F2(x_i, x_{i+1})). \quad (34)$$

The domain considered here is $x_i \in [1 - \omega, 1 + \omega]$. Similarly to above, model samples are generated in the range $x, y \in [-1, 1]$ which are linearly scaled and translated to the domain of the function. The objective function can then be expressed as

$$g(\mathbf{x}) = F\left(\omega(\mathbf{x} - \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 \end{bmatrix}^T)\right). \quad (35)$$

When finding minima in this function, we use the Jacobian but not the Hessian due to the complexity of the function. The Jacobian is given as

$$\mathbf{J}_i(\mathbf{x}) = \omega[0.001F2(x_i, x_j)(200x_i^3 - 200x_i x_j + x_i - 1) \quad (36)$$

$$- 0.1F2(x_j, x_i)(x_j^2 - x_i) \quad (37)$$

$$+ 2(200x_i^3 - 200x_i x_j + x_i - 1) \sin(F2(x_i, x_j)) \quad (38)$$

$$- 200(x_j^2 - x_i) \sin(F2(x_j, x_i)), \quad (39)$$

where $(i, j) \in [(1, 2), (2, 1)]$. We seek all points $\mathbf{x} \in \mathcal{X}$, where $\mathcal{X} \subset \mathbb{R}^D$, such that $g(\mathbf{x})$ is a local minimum. Figure 3 shows the values of $g(\mathbf{x})$ and local minima for this formulation of the Whitley function where $\omega = 0.3$.

FIGURE 3 Value of the Whitley function $g(x, y)$ and locations of local minima for $\omega = 0.3$.

4.1.4 | Rotated Functions

The rotated variations of the Rastrigin, Schwefel, and Whitley functions offer an extra variable parameter for the problem in the angle of rotation, denoted ϕ . Defining the rotation matrix \mathbf{M} as

$$\mathbf{M} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\phi) & -\sin(\phi) \\ \sin(\phi) & \cos(\phi) \end{bmatrix} \quad (40)$$

the expressions for the rotated function rotated around the point \mathbf{x}_0 , and corresponding Jacobian and Hessian, denoted with the subscript R , are

$$g_R(\mathbf{x}) = g(\mathbf{M}^T \times (\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_0) + \mathbf{x}_0), \quad (41)$$

$$\mathbf{J}_R(\mathbf{x}) = \mathbf{M} \times \mathbf{J}(\mathbf{M}^T \times (\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_0) + \mathbf{x}_0), \quad (42)$$

$$\mathbf{H}_R(\mathbf{x}) = (\mathbf{M} \times \mathbf{H}(\mathbf{M}^T \times (\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_0) + \mathbf{x}_0)) \times \mathbf{M}^T + \sum_{i=1}^D \mathbf{J}_i(\mathbf{M}^T \times (\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_0) + \mathbf{x}_0). \quad (43)$$

The Rastrigin function is rotated around the point $\mathbf{x}_0 = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$. The Schwefel function is rotated around the point $\mathbf{x}_0 = \begin{bmatrix} 2 + \delta x & \delta x \end{bmatrix}$, where the Schwefel function is rotated and then shifted. Similarly, the Whitley function is rotated around the point $\mathbf{x}_0 = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$.

4.1.5 | CR5BP

We use the formulation of the CR5BP originally introduced in (Ollongren, 1988) and later studied in terms of its basins of attraction (Zotos & Suraj, 2018). The problem consists of four primary bodies P_i , $i = 0, 1, 2, 3$ with dimensionless masses $m_0 = \beta m$, $m_1 = m_2 = m_3 = m = 1$. To model the fifth body, the system uses a rotating frame of reference with origin at the centre of mass of the primary bodies. The positions of the centres of the primary bodies are $(x_0, y_0) = (0, 0)$, $(x_1, y_1) = (1/\sqrt{3}, 0)$, $(x_2, y_2) = (-1/(2\sqrt{3}), 1/2)$, $(x_3, y_3) = (-1/(2\sqrt{3}), -1/2)$. The fifth body has negligible mass and its position is denoted (x, y) .

As defined in (Ollongren, 1988), the time-independent effective potential function of this problem is

$$\Omega(x, y) = \frac{1}{2} (x^2 + y^2) + k \sum_{i=0}^3 \left[\frac{m_i}{r_i} \right], \quad (44)$$

where

$$k = \frac{1}{3(1 + \beta\sqrt{3})}, \quad (45)$$

$$r_i = \sqrt{(x - x_i)^2 + (y - y_i)^2}, \quad i = 0, 1, 2, 3. \quad (46)$$

The partial derivatives of this potential function are

$$\frac{\partial \Omega}{\partial x} = x - k \sum_{i=0}^3 \frac{m_i(x - x_i)}{r_i^3}, \quad (47)$$

$$\frac{\partial \Omega}{\partial y} = y - k \sum_{i=0}^3 \frac{m_i(y - y_i)}{r_i^3}. \quad (48)$$

In this problem we seek all equilibrium points that are defined by the points where $\frac{\partial \Omega}{\partial x} = 0$ and $\frac{\partial \Omega}{\partial y} = 0$. To locate these points numerically, we also use the second order partial derivatives that are defined as

$$\frac{\partial^2 \Omega}{\partial x^2} = 1 + k \sum_{i=0}^3 \frac{m_i(3(x - x_i)^2 - r_i^2)}{r_i^5}, \quad (49)$$

$$\frac{\partial^2 \Omega}{\partial x \partial y} = \frac{\partial^2 \Omega}{\partial y \partial x} = 3k \sum_{i=0}^3 \frac{m_i(x - x_i)(y - y_i)}{r_i^5}, \quad (50)$$

$$\frac{\partial^2 \Omega}{\partial y^2} = 1 + k \sum_{i=0}^3 \frac{m_i(3(y - y_i)^2 - r_i^2)}{r_i^5}. \quad (51)$$

Defining a mass parameter $\mu = 1/(1 + \beta)$, the value of μ controls the number of equilibrium points present and their stability characteristics. For values of $\mu \in (0, 0.98617275]$ there are 9 equilibrium points. Above this value, when $\mu \in [0.98617276, 1)$ there are 15 equilibrium points. The critical mass parameter of $\mu_{crit} \approx 0.02263467$ affects the stability characteristics of the equilibrium points. For values of μ greater than μ_{crit} , all equilibrium points are unstable, whereas for values below this there are 3 stable equilibria and 6 unstable.

Figures 4 and 5 illustrate the effect of μ on the potential function and locations of equilibrium points. In Figure 4, the mass parameter is $\mu = 0.02$ and there are 9 equilibrium points, three of which are stable. In

Figure 4, the mass parameter is $\mu = 0.992$ and there are 15 equilibrium points that are all unstable.

FIGURE 4 Value of the CR5BP effective potential $\Omega(x, y)$ and locations of equilibrium points for $\mu = 0.02$.

FIGURE 5 Value of the CR5BP effective potential $\Omega(x, y)$ and locations of equilibrium points for $\mu = 0.992$.

4.1.6 | Metastability Problem

To illustrate how this approach can also be used to model metastability of points, we derive a potential function that exhibits metastable behaviour in some critical points. This function is defined by a number of well components that indicate stable or metastable equilibrium points. Using similar notation as above in the CR5BP, the potential function is defined as

$$\Omega(x, y) = 0.01(x^2 + y^2) - \sum_{i=1}^{N_w} w_i \exp(-15((x - x_i)^2 + (y - y_i)^2)), \quad (52)$$

where N_w is the number of well components, w_i is a scaling factor that controls the depth of each component, and (x_i, y_i) are the locations of the well components that in turn define the locations of the equilibrium points. The equation of motion of this system is then expressed as

$$\ddot{\mathbf{x}} = -\nabla\Omega(\mathbf{x}), \quad (53)$$

where $\mathbf{x} = (x, y)$ and the partial derivatives of the potential function are

$$\frac{\partial\Omega}{\partial x} = 0.02x + \sum_{i=1}^{N_w} 30w_i(x - x_i) \exp(-15((x - x_i)^2 + (y - y_i)^2)), \quad (54)$$

$$\frac{\partial\Omega}{\partial y} = 0.02y + \sum_{i=1}^{N_w} 30w_i(y - y_i) \exp(-15((x - x_i)^2 + (y - y_i)^2)). \quad (55)$$

As in the CR5BP, equilibrium points are located where $\frac{\partial\Omega}{\partial x} = 0$ and $\frac{\partial\Omega}{\partial y} = 0$. The formulation used here consists of two well potentials with $w_1 = 2$ and $(x_1, y_1) = (-0.7, 0)$ defining the stable well and $w_2 = \mu$ and $(x_2, y_2) = (0.7, 0)$ defining the metastable well. In this case the parameter μ directly controls the depth of the metastable well, which in turn affects its stability characteristics. There are 3 equilibrium points located along the x-axis. The stable equilibrium point is located near x_1 at $x \approx -0.7$. The locations of the unstable and metastable equilibrium points vary with μ with the unstable point located between the stable and metastable points. Unlike the other test cases, since this problem only has three equilibrium points we assume the location of these points is known a priori for all values of μ . Instead of aiming to find new points, in this problem we are interested in modelling the metastability characteristics of the relevant equilibrium point. The scope of the test is to prove the capability of the flow model to learn the stability properties conditional to the uncertain parameter μ , which is essential to then search only for critical points with specific stability characteristics.

Figure 6 shows the potential function and locations of equilibrium points in this function for $\mu = 0.1$. To show more clearly the locations of the equilibrium points, Figure 7 shows a one-dimensional view of the potential function when $y = 0$.

4.2 | Simulation setup

All simulations were run on an Ubuntu 24.04 computer with an Intel Core i9-13900KS CPU and 64GB RAM. In each of the scenarios and

FIGURE 6 Value of the metastable potential $\Omega(x, y)$ and locations of equilibrium points for $\mu = 0.1$.

FIGURE 7 Value of the metastable potential $\Omega(x, 0)$ for $\mu = 0.1$.

test cases shown here, certain model hyperparameters were the same across all runs. These are shown in Table 1. The flow-based models use a m -function parameterised as a DNN with hyperparameters as indicated in Table 1. The optimiser used for training the networks is the Adam optimiser as implemented in the Tensorflow python library. The size of the network in terms of number of hidden layers and hidden nodes was selected as a reasonable trade-off between the model's capacity to learn more complex distributions and the time required to train. Similarly, the learning rate of 10^{-3} was found to be suitable for allowing the model to converge well to the desired distribution. The selected batch size also means that the model can train more quickly on the entire dataset at each epoch than for smaller batch sizes while still converging effectively.

TABLE 1 Model hyperparameters used in all training scenarios.

Hyperparameter	Value
Hidden layers	3
Nodes per layer	512
Activation function	ReLU
Initial prior covariance	1
Learning rate	0.001
Batch size	256

When creating training data and evaluating posterior density, each component of the posterior distribution is defined as having a spherical covariance with a scale of 0.001. Finding desired points from samples requires the use of a local minimisation or root finding procedure. In the Rastrigin and Schwefel functions, the local minimisation uses the Newton-CG method. In the Whitley function, which does not include information on the Hessian, the local minimisation uses the BFGS method. In the CR5BP, the root finder uses the Levenberg-Marquardt method. All of these optimisation methods are implemented in the SciPy Python library (Virtanen et al., 2020).

4.3 | Training on a subset of minima

In the first training scenario, we begin by randomly sampling in the physical space of the system of interest and find local minima or equilibrium points. With this subset of all the desired points, we iteratively train a model to find all the other desired points in the system. Table 2 lists the relevant hyperparameters for retraining on the Rastrigin/Schwefel/Whitley functions and CR5BP. N_0 is the initial population size, which is obtained from local minimisations starting from random samples. This population size was chosen to be much smaller than the total number of minima in the function, but enough to give some initial information on the distribution of minima to the model. At each retraining iteration the model is retrained on the dataset, consisting of samples around all known minima, for N_{epoch} training epochs. Again this value is a suitable trade-off between allowing the model to converge on the distribution and minimising the training time. Furthermore, too many training epochs may result in overfitting to the known points, which is also undesirable. After retraining, the model generates N_{samp} samples which are then filtered. Samples outwith the specified domain are removed as well as samples where the euclidean distance to a known minima is less than r_t . This latter filtering criterion aims to reduce how often the model re-samples known minima, but due to the nature of the local optimisation, samples outwith this radius can still converge on known minima. Starting from each of the remaining samples, the local optimisation finds a local minimum. If the minimum is not already known, it gets added to the dataset and training continues.

These hyperparameters were selected after testing a few different model configurations as they gave a suitable level of performance. One of the main considerations in choosing these parameters was the

training time. Although the results that follow consider the number of function evaluations in the local optimisations, there is an additional computational cost in the training of the model. Modern software packages for machine learning have very efficient implementations of gradient descent for neural network parameters, but the total cost over the process of retraining is still not negligible. As an illustrative example, performing 16 epochs of training with the hyperparameters and hardware listed above and 2^{13} points in the dataset takes around 23 seconds to complete. The number of retraining iterations ranged between 2 and 67 for the model trained with function values depending on the complexity of the problem, corresponding to training times of between 46 seconds and 26 minutes. One of the benefits of training a model as opposed to other forms of global search, as will be shown in later results, is that the trained model can one-shot sample new points with some desired properties. Although the computational time accounting for model training may be similar or greater than random sampling, especially in these smaller scale problems, this sampling capability of the model is still a key benefit.

TABLE 2 Model parameters

Parameter	Value	
	Rastrigin/Schwefel/Whitley	CR5BP
N_0	8	4
N_{epoch}	16	16
N_{samp}	512	256
r_t	$\frac{0.5}{\omega} / \frac{40}{\omega} / 0.006$	0.006

We compare the results of the iterative retraining of the flow model to randomly sampling from a uniform distribution and starting a local search from each random sample. The key metric is the number of function evaluations, N_{fev} , to find all desired points in a given domain. Table 3 lists the test scenarios and their respective numbers of desired points, as well as the maximum value of each component x_i used when sampling and training. For the three functions, Rastrigin, Schwefel, and Whitley, the rotation ϕ is set to 0. Each scenario and model configuration ran for 32 different random seeds.

Figures 8 - 11 show the mean, minimum, and maximum number of function evaluations for each problem. In most cases, including information on the relevant function value, where $\hat{\mathbf{x}} = [\mathbf{x} \ g(\mathbf{s}_k)]$, or $\hat{\mathbf{x}} = [\mathbf{x} \ \Omega(\mathbf{s}_k)]$, decreases the average number of function evaluations compared to only including \mathbf{x} in the posterior distribution. In the simplest case of the Rastrigin function where minima are regularly spaced, random sampling uses fewer function evaluations on average than the model retraining. However, for the Schwefel and Whitley functions, which have densely packed minima in certain regions, the models trained with function values use fewer function evaluations on average than random sampling. This difference in N_{fev} is more noticeable at larger values of the parameter ω when there are more minima. Since

TABLE 3 Number of desired points in each of the test scenarios.

Problem	Parameter	Number of desired points	$\max x_i$
Rastrigin	$\omega = 3.5$	49	1
Rastrigin	$\omega = 5.5$	121	1
Rastrigin	$\omega = 7.5$	225	1
Schwefel	$\omega = 1100$	49	1
Schwefel	$\omega = 2700$	121	1
Schwefel	$\omega = 4300$	196	1
Whitley	$\omega = 0.2$	29	1
Whitley	$\omega = 0.3$	143	1
Whitley	$\omega = 0.4$	462	1
CR5BP	$\mu = 0.02$	9	0.8
CR5BP	$\mu = 0.992$	15	1.3

the equilibrium points in the CR5BP are more sparse, particularly in the case with 9 equilibrium points, there is less potential benefit to the adaptive sampling strategy of the model. Nevertheless, in the case where $\mu = 0.992$ with 15 equilibrium points, both cases of the model trained with and without potential function values require fewer function evaluations on average than random sampling. Since in dynamical astronomy the value of the mass of n-body systems can be uncertain, the efficient discovery of equilibrium solutions under uncertainty is key to understand their dynamics.

FIGURE 8 Mean number of function evaluations, N_{fev} on the Rastrigin function across 32 random seeds with $\omega = 3.5, 5.5, 7.5$. Error bars indicate minimum and maximum N_{fev} .

Table 4 shows statistics of two tailed t-tests comparing the number of function evaluations for the model retrained with function values and random sampling. For all values of ω in the Rastrigin function, random sampling has a lower mean number of function evaluations. In the Schwefel function with $\omega = 1100$ and the Whitley function with $\omega = 0.2$, the difference in mean function evaluations is not statistically

FIGURE 10 Mean number of function evaluations, N_{fev} on the Whitley function across 32 random seeds with $\omega = 0.2, 0.3, 0.4$. Error bars indicate minimum and maximum N_{fev} .

significant. However, at the larger values of ω in these functions, the difference in mean function evaluations is statistically significant and noticeably larger than for the lowest value. In the CR5BP with $\mu = 0.02$, random sampling has a slightly lower mean N_{fev} , but this difference is not statistically significant. When $\mu = 0.992$ and there are 15 equilibrium points, the model has a much lower mean N_{fev} and the difference is statistically significant.

The models' performance could be further improved by tuning their hyperparameters for each problem. However, for larger scale problems this would be impractical. Although the hyperparameters shown here were not tuned to give the best performance on a single problem, the

FIGURE 11 Mean number of function evaluations, N_{fev} on the CR5BP across 32 random seeds with $\mu = 0.02, 0.992$. Error bars indicate minimum and maximum N_{fev} .

TABLE 4 Results of two tailed T tests of the number of function evaluations between model retraining with function values and random sampling. Negative values of t-statistic indicate a lower mean for model retraining.

	t-statistic	p-value
Rastrigin $\omega = 3.5$	2.18	3.34×10^{-2}
Rastrigin $\omega = 5.5$	4.02	1.60×10^{-4}
Rastrigin $\omega = 7.5$	4.15	1.02×10^{-4}
Schwefel $\omega = 1100$	-0.157	0.876
Schwefel $\omega = 2700$	-5.15	2.87×10^{-6}
Schwefel $\omega = 4300$	-5.65	4.38×10^{-7}
Whitley $\omega = 0.2$	-1.21	0.231
Whitley $\omega = 0.3$	-6.08	8.29×10^{-8}
Whitley $\omega = 0.4$	-12.5	5.29×10^{-15}
CR5BP $\mu = 0.02$	0.152	0.880
CR5BP $\mu = 0.992$	-5.34	1.40×10^{-6}

approach of model retraining can still reduce the number of function evaluations compared to random sampling for more complex distributions of desired points.

4.4 | Training with uncertain parameters

In the case of the Rastrigin, Schwefel, and Whitley functions, the uncertain parameters are the scaling parameter ω and the rotation ϕ . For the CR5BP, the uncertain parameter is the mass parameter μ . The training data consists of samples around all the desired points for certain values

of each parameter, with the parameter values normalised between -1 and 1 as the conditional label. The normalised values of ω and ϕ used in training are $[\pm 1, \pm 0.8, \pm 0.4, 0]$. For the CR5BP, the normalised values of μ are $[\pm 1, \pm 0.75, \pm 0.5, \pm 0.25, 0]$. Table 5 shows the range of parameter values for each problem.

TABLE 5 Ranges of uncertain parameters.

	Rastrigin	Schwefel	Whitley	CR5BP
Min. ω	3.5	1100	0.2	
Max. ω	4.5	1800	0.3	
Min. ϕ	0	0	0	
Max. ϕ	10	10	10	
Min. μ				0.005
Max. μ				0.995

As above, the metrics for assessing the test performance are the number of function evaluations to find all desired points for a given value of parameters. When testing the performance of trained models, we used values of the uncertain parameters that were not used in training. The normalised values of ω for testing are $[\pm 0.6]$ and the normalised values of ϕ are $[\pm 0.9, \pm 0.7, \pm 0.6, \pm 0.5, \pm 0.3, \pm 0.2, \pm 0.1]$. In the CR5BP, the normalised values of μ for testing are $[\pm 0.9, \pm 0.8, \pm 0.7, \pm 0.6, \pm 0.4, \pm 0.3, \pm 0.2, \pm 0.1, 0.99]$. In this case, the normalised value of μ as 0.99 is used as a test case where there are 15 equilibrium points. All other values of normalised μ for testing have 9 equilibrium points. Models were trained with 8 different random seeds for 500 episodes and results are shown for the best performing seed in terms of log-likelihood.

Figures 12 and 13 show the performance comparison of the model and random sampling in the Rastrigin function over a range of rotations ϕ for two different values of ω . In both cases the mean N_{fev} remains below 1000 across all values of ϕ . As well as having a lower N_{fev} on average than random sampling in both cases, the model shows less variation in the number of function evaluations as indicated by the shaded regions.

Figures 12 and 13 show the performance comparison of the model and random sampling in the Schwefel function. Unlike in the Rastrigin function, in this case the model performs similarly or worse than the random sampling across most values of ϕ used for testing. This is likely due to the Schwefel function rotations being around a shifted origin, which causes the dense regions of minima in this function to move outwith the domain of interest for certain magnitudes of rotation. For example, when $\omega = 1660$ and $\phi = 0.5^\circ$ there are 64 minima and when $\phi = 9.5^\circ$ there are 48 minima. This highlights that, for certain types of parametric uncertainty where the distribution and number of desired points change substantially, the model conditioned on parameters may not capture this distribution as effectively.

Figures 16 and 17 show the performance comparison of the model and random sampling in the Whitley function. In the case when $\omega =$

FIGURE 12 Trend in the mean number of function evaluations on the Rastrigin function across 32 random seeds with $\omega = 3.7$ and varying ϕ . Shaded area indicates ± 1 standard deviation.

FIGURE 14 Trend in the mean number of function evaluations on the Schwefel function across 32 random seeds with $\omega = 1240$ and varying ϕ . Shaded area indicates ± 1 standard deviation.

FIGURE 13 Trend in the mean number of function evaluations on the Rastrigin function across 32 random seeds with $\omega = 4.3$ and varying ϕ . Shaded area indicates ± 1 standard deviation.

FIGURE 15 Trend in the mean number of function evaluations on the Schwefel function across 32 random seeds with $\omega = 1660$ and varying ϕ . Shaded area indicates ± 1 standard deviation.

0.22, the model has a consistently lower N_{fev} on average with less variation than random sampling. For the larger value of $\omega = 0.28$, the distributions of N_{fev} are closer together across the range of ϕ . At some values of ϕ , the standard deviation of N_{fev} for the model is noticeably larger than that of random sampling, but the average N_{fev} is still lower for the model across all values of ϕ .

Figure 18 shows the performance comparison of the model and random sampling for the CR5BP with varying mass parameter μ . At all values of μ the model has a lower average N_{fev} than random sampling with generally lower variance. When μ is between 0.8 and 0.95, the average N_{fev} for random sampling decreases substantially compared to

values of $\mu < 0.8$. However, above the critical value of μ where there are 15 equilibrium points, the average N_{fev} of random sampling increases significantly. This is also the case for the model, but it still has far fewer N_{fev} on average - 612 compared to 2757 for random sampling. These results show that, by only training on a few values of uncertain parameters, the flow-based model can capture the distribution of critical points across a range of these parameters. This can be used to generate all critical points for any values of the uncertain parameters within a desired range.

FIGURE 16 Trend in the mean number of function evaluations on the Whitley function across 32 random seeds with $\omega = 0.22$ and varying ϕ . Shaded area indicates ± 1 standard deviation.

FIGURE 18 Trend in the mean number of function evaluations on the CR5BP across 32 random seeds with varying μ . Shaded area indicates ± 1 standard deviation.

FIGURE 17 Trend in the mean number of function evaluations on the Whitley function across 32 random seeds with $\omega = 0.28$ and varying ϕ . Shaded area indicates ± 1 standard deviation.

4.5 | Training with class labels

The labels for equilibrium points in the CR5BP are their stability, which is either unstable, $c = [1 \ 0]$, or stable, $c = [0 \ 1]$. In the Rastrigin, Schwefel, and Whitley functions, labels are assigned based on their respective function value $g(\mathbf{x})$ at the desired point. Each function defines 3 classes of minima, with bin edges shown in Table 6. Values of $g(\mathbf{x}) \leq L_{0-1}$ are assigned $c = [1 \ 0 \ 0]$, values of $L_{0-1} < g(\mathbf{x}) \leq L_{1-2}$ are assigned $c = [0 \ 1 \ 0]$, and values of $g(\mathbf{x}) > L_{1-2}$ are assigned $c = [0 \ 0 \ 1]$.

The normalised values of ω and ϕ and their respective ranges used when training and testing with labels are the same as above when

TABLE 6 Ranges of function values for assigning labels in the benchmark global optimisation problems.

	Min.	L_{0-1}	L_{1-2}	Max.
Rastrigin	0	0.45	0.9	1.999
Schwefel	-6692	-2000	-1000	710.7
Whitley	0	0.15	0.5	3.650

training with uncertain parameters. As before, for each value of the parameters in the dataset we assume all minima are known, but not necessarily with their corresponding label. We test the performance of the model in three different training scenarios: two fully supervised and one semi-supervised. In the first supervised training scenario, training data consists of entirely labelled data for all training values of ω and ϕ . The other supervised training scenario also uses entirely labelled training data, but only for normalised values of ω of $[\pm 1, \pm 0.4]$. These training scenarios are referred to as n7 and n4 respectively, indicating the number of values of ω in the training dataset. In the semi-supervised training scenario, normalised values of ω of $[\pm 1, \pm 0.4]$ are labelled for all values of ϕ and the remainder of the training data are unlabelled.

In the CR5BP, since the values of μ with stable equilibrium points only occupy a small range of the possible values of μ , when training with labels the range is $\mu \in [0.001, 0.05]$. Similarly to the other functions, we compared two supervised and one semi-supervised training scenarios. In the semi-supervised scenario, the normalised values of μ of $[\pm 1, \pm 0.3]$ in the training data are labelled and the unlabelled values of μ are $[\pm 0.8, \pm 0.6, \pm 0.4, \pm 0.2, 0]$. The supervised n7 scenario has values of μ of $[\pm 1, \pm 0.8, \pm 0.4, 0]$ and the other supervised n4 scenario has values of μ of $[\pm 1, \pm 0.3]$. Models were trained with 8 different random seeds for 100 episodes.

FIGURE 19 Negative log likelihood vs error rate of samples in the Rastrigin function.

FIGURE 21 Negative log likelihood vs error rate of samples in the Whitley function.

FIGURE 20 Negative log likelihood vs error rate of samples in the Schwefel function.

FIGURE 22 Negative log likelihood vs error rate of samples in the CR5BP.

The supervised or semi-supervised training with class labels aims to generate new points of a specified class. When generating samples, the model uses the label of the relevant class and filters samples that are outwith the desired range or have a higher likelihood for another label. Samples are evaluated by how close they are to a point of the corresponding sample class. Let d_{ij} denote the minimum euclidean distance between a sample of predicted class i with a desired point of true class j for the sampled values of uncertain parameters. The true class label c

associated with the sampled point is then defined as:

$$c = \arg \min_j (d_{ij}). \quad (56)$$

The case where $j = i$ indicates a correct classification, whereas $j \neq i$ is a misclassification. For each test case, models generated 1000 samples with each class label. The overall accuracy of a model is the proportion of samples with the correct class.

The class boundaries shown in Table 6 were selected arbitrarily with the aim of roughly balancing the number of points in each class across

the training and test datasets. This is highlighted in Table 7 which shows the percentage of points in each class, denoted $\%_{point}$, for each problem. Also shown in Table 7 are the percentage of sampled points with the corresponding class label defined by equation 56 when uniformly sampling the domain, denoted $\%_{samp}$. In the Rastrigin function, both proportions are similar for each class label. However, in the other functions where desired points are spread less uniformly over the domain, this is not the case. In the Whitley function and CR5BP, over 75% of sampled points are closest to a single class label. Sampling from a trained flow-based model conditioned on the class label should improve the sampling rate for these minority classes.

TABLE 7 Percentage of points with each class label across training and test sets and the percentage of randomly sampled points where the closest class label is c .

	C0		C1		C2	
	$\%_{point}$	$\%_{samp}$	$\%_{point}$	$\%_{samp}$	$\%_{point}$	$\%_{samp}$
Rastrigin	34.7	37.1	36.1	35.1	29.2	27.8
Schwefel	37.3	54.7	27.4	27.6	35.3	17.8
Whitley	32.7	75.3	32.8	16.9	34.4	7.9
CR5BP	85.7	76.5	14.3	23.5	-	-

As well as the classification accuracy of samples, we are interested in how well the model generalises and can sample values of uncertain parameters away from the training data. A model that exactly replicates the training data would have perfect accuracy, but obviously would not be useful for finding new desired points. To quantify how well a model generalises, we evaluate the model log-likelihood for desired points conditioned on their true class label at values of the uncertain parameters that are not in the training data.

Figures 19 - 22 show scatter plots of the negative log-likelihood of unseen points and the error rate of samples in each of the problems. Across all of the problems, the supervised $n7$ training scenario performs best in general both in terms of generalisation and accuracy. This is to be expected since this scenario contains the most labelled training data. Although the semi-supervised training scenario generally performs worst in terms of accuracy, its generalisation is generally better than that of the supervised $n4$ scenario. This shows that including unlabelled data points when these are available can improve the sampling generalisation of the model, but there is a trade-off in terms of the classification accuracy of samples. For the problems considered here, the true labels for a desired point are inexpensive to determine and so fully supervised training is feasible. However, if class labels were some characteristic of a critical point that is more expensive to determine, semi-supervised training would provide a way to find more critical points, but with less certainty about their true class.

The following results use models for each problem and training scenario that are pareto-optimal in terms of the negative log-likelihood and error rate. Figures 23 - 26 show the confusion matrices for the 1000

sampled points in each problem and training scenario. The larger values along the diagonal in each matrix indicate most samples are correctly classified. In the Rastrigin function, there is the most significant difference in classification accuracy between the training scenarios. Most of the misclassified points are for neighbouring classes, e.g. class C2 misclassified as C1 or C1 misclassified as C0. Due to the funnel shape of the Rastrigin function, these classes also share a boundary in physical space and therefore some misclassification at these boundaries would be expected. This is also the case in the Whitley function, although the overall accuracy is still higher in this problem than for the Rastrigin function. In all cases, the proportion of correctly sampled points with a certain class is higher than the proportion from purely random sampling, as desired.

To further investigate the failure modes of the model sampling, we show some additional statistics on the misclassified samples. There are two reasons for a misclassified sample: either a desired point of a different class is closer to the sample, or there are no points of the predicted sample class at the sampled values of uncertain parameters. The latter case is only applicable for the CR5BP, where above the critical value of μ there are no stable equilibria, and the Whitley function, where for a subset of the parameters there are no points with class label C2.

In the Whitley function, the number of points sampled with class C2 where there are no minima of this class are 0, 1, and 1 in the supervised $n7$, supervised $n4$, and semi-supervised training scenarios respectively. This represents a very low proportion of the misclassifications in this problem. In the CR5BP, the number of points sampled with a stable class label and $\mu > \mu_{crit}$ are 3, 29, and 138 in the supervised $n7$, supervised $n4$, and semi-supervised training scenarios respectively. For the semi-supervised training scenario, this is the reason for 79% of the misclassified points. Without more training data, it is difficult for the model to establish the boundary between values of μ with and without stable equilibria. Although there are fewer misclassified samples of this type in the supervised $n4$ training scenario, as shown above this model is more likely to sample points near the training data.

In the other failure mode, the sample is simply closer to a desired point of the incorrect class. As discussed above, this might be the case where classes share a boundary and the samples are near the boundary. We wish to quantify how close misclassified samples are to the desired points of the correct class. Let $d_{ij|c=k}$ denote the minimum distance between a sample of predicted class i with a desired point of true class j , where the nearest desired point is of true class k . The misclassification distance \hat{d}_{ij} is defined as

$$\hat{d}_{ij} = \frac{1}{N_1} \sum d_{ij|c=i} - \frac{1}{N_2} \sum d_{ij|c=i}, \quad (57)$$

where N_1 is the number of samples of predicted class i with true class i and N_2 is the number of samples of predicted class j with true class i . This distance quantifies the difference between the average minimum distance of correct samples of class i to desired points of class j and the average minimum distance of incorrect samples of class i with predicted class j to desired points of class j . When $i = j$, the misclassification distance is 0. Where there are no misclassified points of true class i for predicted sample class j , the misclassification distance is undefined. A

FIGURE 23 Confusion matrices of sampled points in the Rastrigin function for three different training scenarios.

FIGURE 24 Confusion matrices of sampled points in the Schwefel function for three different training scenarios.

positive value of \hat{d}_{ij} indicates the misclassified samples are closer to the predicted class on average than correct samples of the same true class.

Figures 27 - 30 show the misclassification distances for each problem and training scenario. The magnitude of these distances varies across the problems and classes, but in every case the distance is positive except for in the Whitley function for the supervised n7 training scenario. The case where $i = 2$ and $j = 0$ for this problem has a negative misclassification distance, indicating the misclassified samples with predicted class C2 tend to be further from the desired class than true samples of class C0. Part of the reason for this is due to the shape of distribution of minima with the highest values of $g(x)$. These have two separate regions in the top left (near (-1,1)) and bottom right (near (1,-1)) of the domain as shown in Figure 3. In these cases, the flow-based model will tend to “connect” the two separate regions with areas of slightly higher

likelihood and will therefore sometimes generate samples in this region. The number of misclassified samples in this case is still relatively low at only 15 of the 1000 total samples of predicted class C2.

4.6 | Training with metastability class labels

The final test case is the metastability problem. In this problem, we are interested in quantifying the metastability of an equilibrium point and how this varies with the system’s uncertain parameters. As a simple measure of metastability, we first propagate many trajectories starting from points within the potential well of the metastable equilibrium point for a fixed time period. Some trajectories will remain near the equilibrium point with behaviour similar to a stable equilibrium point. However,

FIGURE 25 Confusion matrices of sampled points in the Whitley function for three different training scenarios.

FIGURE 26 Confusion matrices of sampled points in the CR5BP for three different training scenarios.

other trajectories will move away from the equilibrium point and begin to orbit the other, stable equilibrium point. Figure 31 illustrates both these scenarios when $\mu = 0.05$. Over the time horizon simulated here, Trajectory 1 remains in orbit around the metastable equilibrium point. Trajectory 2 orbits the metastable point for a short time before moving away from its basin towards the stable point.

After simulating multiple trajectories for a given value of μ , the metastability measure of the equilibrium point is then defined as the proportion of trajectories that remain within a certain distance of the well point $(x_2, y_2) = (0.7, 0)$. This value is denoted c_{ms} . A value of $c_{ms} = 0$ indicates an unstable point where no trajectories remain near the equilibrium point and $c_{ms} = 1$ indicates a stable point. Values of $0 < c_{ms} < 1$ define a metastable point that is given the class label $c = \begin{bmatrix} 1 - c_{ms} & c_{ms} \end{bmatrix}$. In this formulation, the metastability measure of a point is computed for

each value of the uncertain system parameters used for training. It is also possible to define the level of metastability taking into account the uncertainty in these parameters. In this case every trajectory would be subject to a different value of the uncertain parameter, but this is not considered in this work. Note that the computation of the meta-stability of a point is an expensive process because it requires the propagation of an ensemble of trajectories. It is, therefore, desirable to learn the distribution of the points and conditionally generate samples only in the neighbourhood of the ones with the required stability properties.

Trajectories were simulated for values of μ in the range $0 \leq \mu \leq 0.1$, where $\mu = 0$ represents the case where there is no equilibrium point resulting in $c_{ms} = 0$. For each value of μ we ran 500 trajectories of 5000 timesteps with a step size of 0.01. The initial states were uniformly sampled within a radius of $\sqrt{2}\sigma_w$, where $\sigma_w = \sqrt{\frac{1}{15}}$ with zero initial

FIGURE 27 Misclassification distances of sampled points in the Rastrigin function for three different training scenarios.

FIGURE 28 Misclassification distances of sampled points in the Schwefel function for three different training scenarios.

velocity. The threshold distance for determining if a trajectory stays within the metastable well was 0.5. Figure 32 shows how the metastability measure c_{ms} varies over this range of μ . As indicated in the figure, the data used to train the flow-based model consisted of points near all three of the equilibrium points with their respective class labels for 7 different values of μ . In this problem the model was trained in a fully supervised manner with only labelled training data. This was necessary since the semi-supervised training approach described in Section 3.3 requires enumerating over all classes, which is not possible for metastable class labels.

A total of 8 models were trained for 100 episodes with different random seeds and results are shown for the best performing model in terms of log-likelihood. Figure 33 shows the values of μ and x for model samples conditioned on values of $c_{ms} = 0, 0.5, 0.6, 0.7, 0.8, 0.9, 0.95, 1$. Due to the continuous values of the class labels, it is not possible to compute distance metrics in the same way as for the problems described above.

However, we can still evaluate the samples qualitatively. The figure shows that the samples follow the locations of the equilibrium points in physical space (i.e. their x coordinates) very well for most values of c_{ms} . We can also see that the samples conditioned on stable ($c_{ms} = 1$) and unstable ($c_{ms} = 0$) class labels are near the correct equilibrium points, with some of the stable samples appearing at the metastable equilibrium point for higher values of μ . Values of c_{ms} closer to 0.5 for the metastable point appear clustered near the metastable point as desired. However, as $c_{ms} \rightarrow 1$ the model starts sampling near the stable equilibrium point and at values of x between both points. This is similar to the behaviour described above where the model will tend to “connect” separate regions of the same class. Despite these cases, most of the model samples appear to match the true distribution well. It is also to be noted that from the point of view of the analysis of the dynamical system and identification of transitions between critical points, these connections

FIGURE 29 Misclassification distances of sampled points in the Whitley function for three different training scenarios.

FIGURE 30 Misclassification distances of sampled points in the CR5BP for three different training scenarios.

are actually desirable, albeit they produce samples with label classes in between the two equilibria.

For a given metastable equilibrium point, we may wish to know its measure of metastability over a range of values of the uncertain parameter. Given a class label $c = [1 - c_{ms} \ c_{ms}]$, we can determine the model's estimated likelihood of the metastable equilibrium point for a range of values of μ . The value of μ corresponding to the specified metastability measure is then estimated as the value of μ with the highest model likelihood $p_X(x)$. This is illustrated in Figure 34 for a conditional label of $c = [0.1 \ 0.9]$. The model evaluates the likelihood of the equilibrium point over 100 values of μ linearly spaced between 0.0035 and 0.1 and shows a clear spike in likelihood near the value corresponding to the class label. The model can also evaluate the inverse function and, for a metastable equilibrium point with a specified value of μ , estimate

the likelihood for a range of class labels $c = [1 - c_{ms} \ c_{ms}]$. Results are shown here for both cases.

Figure 35 shows the model estimate of μ for the metastable equilibrium point conditioned on $c = [1 - c_{ms} \ c_{ms}]$ for values of c_{ms} in the range $0.2 \leq c_{ms} \leq 1$. Most of the predicted values of μ closely match the empirical trend in the data. The estimated value of μ when $c_{ms} = 1$ 0.08, which is lower than the value suggested in the empirical trend. However, when sampling over μ and evaluating the metastability measure, the model captures the trend better for the higher values of c_{ms} . This is highlighted in Figure 35 which shows the model estimated value of c_{ms} of the metastable point for values of μ in the range $0.005 \leq \mu \leq 0.1$. Model estimates of c_{ms} for values of μ in the training dataset are very close to the correct value as expected. The values not seen in the dataset show the model captures the empirical trend well. These results show that the conditional flow-based model is capable of

FIGURE 31 Example trajectories starting from points in the metastable potential well for $\mu = 0.05$.

FIGURE 33 Generated samples conditioned on different values of c_{ms} in the metastability problem.

FIGURE 32 Variation of the metastability measure with μ for the metastable equilibrium point in the example problem.

FIGURE 34 Model estimated likelihood of an equilibrium point for varying values of μ conditioned on $c = [0.1 \ 0.9]$.

sampling points with desired metastability characteristics. In addition, the conditional flow-based model provides an effective means to estimate the trend in metastability of a point without the need to run many trajectory propagations.

5 | CONCLUSIONS

This work introduced an approach to finding all critical points, with given properties, of a scalar function using a generative flow-based model. Starting from a subset of critical points, we implemented an iterative procedure that incrementally finds new points by alternating sampling

and retraining of the model. It was demonstrated that, depending on the structure of the scalar function, as the number of minima increases, the flow-based generative model is more efficient than a purely uniform sampling of the search space. The major inefficiency in the generation, which requires further improvement, was found to be the re-generation of already discovered minima. When the discovery of minima was conditional to uncertain parameters, that are changing the structure of the scalar function or the number of minima, we demonstrated that the flow-based model allows one-shot generation of samples with desired characteristics and can be significantly more efficient than the uniform sampling. It was shown that the conditional flow-based model can effectively sample points with varying values of uncertain parameters or class labels, including cases where the class label is not binary but has

FIGURE 35 Model estimate of μ for varying values of the metastability measure for the metastable equilibrium point in the example problem.

FIGURE 36 Model estimate of metastability measure for varying values of μ for the metastable equilibrium point in the example problem.

a continuous value, as is the case for the stable and unstable points of an n -body problem. We also demonstrated the sampling of minima with metastable properties in a simple case where the stability properties depend on a single uncertain parameter.

This work used low dimensional problems that are tractable to solve with simple methods, for example through uniform sampling. This was intentional because it allowed us to inspect the results of the generative conditional discovery of critical points in cases in which all the minima and their properties could be easily computed. At the same time we showed that when the underlying structure of the scalar function $g(\mathbf{x})$ is complex, even in low dimensions, learning the distribution of the critical points is advantageous compared to a uniform sampling. Given

that covering the whole search space with the same density of samples grows exponentially with the number of dimensions, it is expected that learning a model of the distribution of the critical points becomes progressively more efficient. Still the re-generation of already discovered points is something to improve in the future.

Future work will also investigate the applicability of the proposed method to larger scale problems. Furthermore, the approach described in this paper used three separate stages of training for finding new critical points, conditioning on uncertain parameters, and conditioning on point characteristics. The next step will be to unify these three steps such that the model can start from a known subset of critical points, with known properties but with the function $g(\mathbf{x})$ subject to uncertainty, and discover new critical points conditioned on both the uncertain parameters and the desired characteristics at the same time.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare no potential conflict of interests.

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